

Finding Solutions to Inherent Contradiction & Dilemmas through Values & Ethics

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Abstract

Since time immemorial, in Indian civilization, character building of an individual has been one of the prime motives of education, as is evident in the ancient time, specially, Vedic, Buddhist, Medieval, and even British time. With the advent of modernity, man has been constantly doing away with his spirit, soul, thus losing values and Ethics, which is the backbone of his own 'being'. Especially in the past few years, while chasing his dreams and proving himself every moment in today's cut-throat competition, the youth has not been able to cope up with this 'pressure' and constantly losing the peace of mind, thus leading to stress, depression or even suicidal cases. To overcome this, academicians, throughout the world, have advocated for inculcating moral or value education, especially in technical professionals, which will help them to 'regain' their lost Ethics. The present paper explores possible ways to overcome this 'state of resignation' and regain Ethics through value education, wavering aspirations, right understanding, which are, undoubtedly, scientific, and form the basis of our very own civilization.

Keywords: Ethics, Value Education, civilization, attitude, science, existence etc.

Introduction

Opinion polls show that, in spite of our society's progressive secularization during the 20th century, values, religion and Ethics continue to play a large part in people's lives. According to some research, the majority of mental health professionals consider Ethics important in their personal lives as well as in their clinical work (Aponte, 1996; Becvar, 1997; Bergin, 1991; Lukoff, Lu, & Turner, 1992; Shafranske & Gorsuch, 1984; Shafranske & Malony, 1990). “There is no existence without Ethics”. But, man's actions, his rush and hurry have already caused much chaos and trouble in the world. Now it's high time to stop and think about our goals, their attainment, and the methods adopted for the same. And, here rises the need of self-exploration.

Self – exploration is the process of finding out what is valuable to me, what is right for me and true for me by investigating within myself.

Self-exploration represents the inner journey into yourself, into your own inner space for understanding you fully and absolutely.

Even we can't say that life is cool and calm, even it is full of challenges, ups and downs. The thing is that why life is difficult for all of us. It doesn't matter where we are born in, may be in a family where we have lots of money, intelligence, an attractive personality, a luminous outlook, or good social associations – none of these give the supernatural key to an easy life being. In some way life teaches us how en route for a perfect solution to all the hurdles whatsoever come in our life. It is up to you only that how you meet the challenges of life. Next thing which comes to our mind – If something happening with us, is because of some reasons or it is simply a series of events.

Ethics begins with a decisive answer to that question. It says that life is not random. There is a pattern and purpose inside every existence. The reason that challenges arise is simple: to make us more aware of our inner purpose. If the ethical answer is true, there should be a ethical solution to every problem- and there is. Let's discuss general human problems and their solutions in light of Ethics-

At the human level, we can see that there continues to be issues in individuals with respect to lack of clarity on life-goals, contradictions and stress, while we at the level of human relationships in the family, we see problems in mutual understanding, increasing mistrust, insecurity and generation gap. Due to lack of right understanding, human beings consider happiness is the accumulation of physical facilities and prosperity is to maximize the accumulation and use of physical facilities. This tendency gives rise to various problems (Sunil Garg, 2012) at four levels of life as mentioned below:

In Individual: Rising stress, depression, anxiety, feeling of loneliness, health issues, short of confidence, addictions & suicides etc.

In Family: Mistrust and disharmony in relationships, breaking up of joint families, dowry killing, female foeticide, divorce, generation gap, negligence of older people etc.

In Society: Corruption, adulteration, violence, racial and ethnic struggle, communalism, social tortures, honour killing, physical abuse, violence, proliferation of lethal weapons and growing incidences of terrorism, wars between nations etc.

In Nature: Deforestation, soil degradation, exploitation of natural resources, pollution, weather imbalances, Global warming, etc.

In current time, human does not have time to think beyond his daily work or nuclear family. He is busy in gathering unwanted and materialistic objects and feels that he is happy. But he is living under constant pressure and fear. The pressure may be to earn good money, to earn good name in society. Pressure may be from peer group or from office to perform well on job. The fear may be getting admission to a proper school and then to a college. The fear of unemployment looms large. He lacks the inner strength, commitment and conviction to face the external threats boldly and wisely.

He considers everything in the universe a kind of energy, and faster movement means getting closed to Ethics. The issues in professional moral principles are becoming very complex in the current scenario. The unethical practices are rapidly increasing and their impact is also becoming far – reaching.

As William Wordsworth once said, child is the father of man; he also proposes that thoughts of an individual shape one's personality and proved that one can live happily and gain Ethics, by doing away with negative forces.

One’s perception towards the things at different times broadens one’s horizons, to look at the same with maturity, critically and analytically, thus leading to attainment of experience and wisdom, knowledge of true happiness. Then, we realize that true happiness lies first within us, then nature, the earth, or the universe.

With the help of self-exploration, we can analyze our weakness and with full potential strengthen our mind and achieve what we want to be. All the problems in our world today have been created by human beings. Whether the problems relate to resource depletion, pollution, and global warming or interpersonal problems- they are consistent and their result is unbearable, that we are living on unhealthy planet, because we are making it unhealthy. We have an answer to each and everything which we are facing today. If I ask you a question which is the predominant fear for all of us, so our answer is very prompt, by saying that the biggest problem which we are facing is the inhuman behavior of human beings. Within our self lays our inner most opinion and passion. Human being among the entire living creature on this planet is regarded as the greatest creature of God. It is because of the virtue of develop brain that he has occupied the paramount position.

Human being a combined unit of body and soul and so it is natural that there must be a perfect harmony between these two to live a happy and peaceful life. As the great saint and preacher Swami Vivekananda start his sermon by saying “**Know thyself**”, so it is foremost need to everyone to have a good conception of him so that he might take a rational view of life and his surroundings through Ethics.

We are surrounded by all types of objects. We try hard to gain these materialistic things. Human aspires to be happy. To attain happiness, he keeps on running from pillar to post. Do the work madly. Even if you ask some successful person – is this world true? He will reply that everything that we see is true. But when he becomes old without money – he will reply to same question that this is all because of his fortune. People forget that everything around us is going to destroy one day whether it is lust, wealth, power, strength, poverty or life. Happiness is all about realizing the fact of brotherhood in every human being. This is not related to language, place, nation, civilization, caste or anything else. This is the link of good thoughts, love, peace and brotherhood. Let us understand the Ethics with the live examples that happen with Swami Vivekananda:

The Swami who had never addressed a huge crowd as this before was nervous. However, when his turn came he mentally bowed down to Goddess Saraswati and began “**Sisters and brothers of America.**” **There was a position acclaim and the hall was resounding with applause. It was this simple sentence with an approach of harmony that got the audience to their feet with admiration. The applause lasted for two full minutes.** It was universality, Ethics and harmony that the Swami expressed as revealed in Hinduism that caught the attraction of one and all.

There have been a few tribulations and trying times in our life. Time, in which we have been forced to deal with the harsh realities of life. They may seem trivial on a much broader scale, but for us they are the turning points of our life that helped us to find our inner well. That inner well helped us deal with the pain of lost loved ones and with things of this world that we alone can’t change. To deal with the strains of taking on too much or too little responsibilities and being distant from the one part of our truly love. At that time there is a need of self-introspection means harmony with yourself to enlighten a stony and sometimes cold heart. So, it is right to say Ethics plays an important role to lighten our heart. To bring harmony in one’s life a person has to allow change. But change itself is preceded by a drive within ‘to’ change. One is fear and the other is love. So many times, when we walk in our life we feel comfort with the situation, it doesn’t matter our path wrong or right, but when we realize that this could be dangerous for our future, then we change our direction, this is called fear; we change according to the situation, and without harmony it is not possible.

We will look into ourselves and find out what we are today, and how this contrast from what we really want to be. If these two are the same, then there is no problem. If on investigation we find that these two are not the same, then it means we are living with this contradiction (of not being what we really want to be) and hence, we need to resolve this contradiction, this conflict within us. Ask yourself this question: “Am I what I really want to be?” When we look into this, we find that mostly we are not what we really want to be. These two are different and each one of us is faced with this contradiction. We are something and we want to be something else. This basic dichotomy, this basic contradiction has to be resolved. This dichotomy creates a conflict in us, which is a continuous cause for our unhappiness. What we are today – is the result of our preconditioning’s, our predispositions, our impressions and our beliefs. What we really want to be – comes from deep within us, which is naturally acceptable to us. It is our natural acceptance only by which we feel related to everyone. It is easy to explore within ourselves, first one has to be in harmony within self then only he can explore the things with right understanding and the blessings of Ethics. Right understanding is necessary for all human beings, for all human beings. Our comprehensive goal is live with right understand and to have a clarity that the other wants to make you happy and prosperous. This is the Comprehensive Human Goal. Ethics will help us to achieve human goal and to live with peace and prosperity, have a feeling more than required.

Here you can verify that if we have right understanding on our top priority then we can decide what to do and how to do through our natural acceptance. Thus, we can achieve happiness (Harmony at individual level) manage well in relations in family with right feelings (Harmony at family level) as well as in society (Harmony at society level). Ultimately, we can consider the right utilization of physical facilities to ensure harmony at the level of nature as all the physical facilities at the deepest level are obtained from nature and now that development doesn’t mean exploitation of nature. In this way we can ensure the harmony at all the four levels leading to almost problem free life.

Conclusion

In order to solve human Contradictions and Dilemmas the present study observes the root cause of human problems which may start from within only not from others. We will find out that nowadays we are talking so much about others, we are wasting our energy in a negative direction and ignoring the need for right understanding, we are ignoring the need to understand happiness correctly. We are ignoring the need to understand and be in the web of healthy relationship which will give us positivity and harmony in an individual. We are not able to see that the need for physical facilities is limited and that, we can have more than what we need! Nowadays we are only talking about how to generate more wealth. We seem to have forgotten that the need to have wealth is connected with the need to keep the body healthy and use it for the right purpose and not for maximizing accumulation for the purpose of sensory enjoyment. In place of working for fearlessness, we are working for strategic powers. We are becoming increasingly more fearful of each other, suspicious that the other human being is out to get me, finish me. We do not have programs to ensure mutual trust among people, which is the basis of fearlessness, peace and harmony in an individual, family, society and nature. The way out is to understand and to live in harmony at all the levels of living, right from oneself to the whole existence. This paves way for moving towards Ethics, and Ethics opens a path for universal human order on earth., which is life giver.

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